

A OPTIMIZATION SYSTEM FOR HUMANITARIAN AID DISTRIBUTION USING DATA MINING ALGORITHMS

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Abstract

The article examines approaches to improving mechanisms for the distribution of humanitarian aid using algorithms for Data Mining. The main task was the development of a web application for the collection and analysis of data on persons in need of humanitarian assistance, in order to ensure the optimal distribution of available resources in accordance with the established priority of vulnerability of population groups. Algorithms of cluster analysis were used to identify persons in need of primary assistance. This facilitates and speeds up the work of volunteers in providing humanitarian aid to the population in the frontline areas, where the distribution of resources is carried out in dynamic, rapidly changing conditions in proportion to requests with a limited number of aid packages.

Keywords: distribution of humanitarian aid, cluster analysis, algorithm k-means, agglomerative hierarchical clustering.

The rapid pace of informatization of modern society is accompanied by the introduction of digital technologies in all spheres of the surrounding reality and in the sphere of accounting and distribution of humanitarian aid in particular. The volume of humanitarian aid has increased sharply in the conditions of military operations on the territory of Ukraine and includes a large number of volunteers, public domestic and international organizations and charitable foundations. The need for immediate assistance to those who need it has increased dramatically. Solving this problem necessitates the creation of information systems to improve demand forecasting and management of humanitarian aid supply and distribution chains [1, 2, 3].

Humanitarian assistance is provided during emergencies and crises and is aimed at saving people's lives and meeting their basic needs for water, food, shelter, hygiene and medical care. At the international level, there are a number of resources to support the provision and distribution of humanitarian aid, such as the UN Humanitarian Data Exchange web platform, the Digital Humanitarian Network website [4, 5]. At the beginning of 2024, the implementation of the Aidmonitor.org web platform for monitoring the provision and distribution of humanitarian aid by international donor organizations began in Ukraine. However, there is a problem in establishing a coordinated interaction of volunteers with people living directly in the front-line territories and the optimal mechanism of aid distribution. This necessitates the development of a data analysis system for persons most in need of assistance in order to improve the mechanisms for the distribution of humanitarian aid.

The purpose of the work is to develop a web application that performs data analysis on persons in need of humanitarian assistance and ensures the optimal distribution of available resources in accordance with the identified priorities in the provision of assistance.

Resource allocation is the process of identifying and allocating available resources among different entities or groups to meet needs or achieve goals in a certain area. Traditional methods of resource allocation include different strategies and approaches: equal distribution and allocations based on needs, economic criteria, established priority, taking into account strategic and political goals. However, traditional methods are unable to take into account complex relationships, analyze big data and make instant decisions, which can lead to suboptimal resource allocation. There is a growing need to use more advanced distribution methods based on Data Mining [6].

When providing humanitarian aid to the population of areas that are close to hostilities, the distribution of resources cannot be centralized and is carried out in dynamic, rapidly changing situations between groups of people in proportion to their requests. In the conditions of a limited amount of humanitarian resources, it is advisable to use cluster analysis algorithms to identify related groups of people in the front-line territories who need priority assistance.

Cluster analysis allows identifying related groups of individuals in a multidimensional space of features that are important to consider when providing assistance. To analyze the vulnerability of population groups in order to determine priorities in the distribution of humanitarian aid, the features that are essential for such an analysis were selected:

- surname: surname of the customer of humanitarian aid;
- danger: level of danger at the place of residence;
- childs: number of children in the family;
- health: total health care expenditure as a % of the total level;
- income: net income per person in family;
- tax: percentage of taxes depending on a person's income;

- age: person's age
- satis: conditional assessment of quality of life.

Data collection in the humanitarian sector in war zones is a challenging task. The web application provides the ability to download information about the needs of people who need help. During the operation of the system, data is accumulated and their cluster analysis is carried out to identify priorities for the distribution of resources, giving preference to the most vulnerable population groups. The system provides for cluster analysis using the k-means algorithm and the agglomerative hierarchical algorithm. The data is processed in real time, which allows for the adjustment of provision of aid strategies.

The system was developed using the Python programming language in the Jupyter Notebook development environment. The Python Flask framework was used to provide backend functionality. The React JavaScript framework, HTML and CSS were used to develop the UI interface and interact with Flask through the server API. Working with files, conducting cluster analysis and assessing its quality, visualization of the obtained results was carried out using the Pandas, Matplotlib, Scikit-learn libraries.

At the stage of data preparation, data cleaning is performed, which includes checking for duplicates and omissions. When duplicates are detected, one of them is deleted, and for omissions, it is replaced by the average arithmetic value of the omitted features. When duplicates are detected, one of them is deleted, and omissions, it is replaced by the average arithmetic value of the omitted feature. In the case of emissions, upper and lower limits have been restrictions introduced.

All data are presented in numerical scales, but in different ranges, so the data is normalization in the range from 0 to 1 using the formula:

$$x'_i = \frac{x_i - x_{\min}}{x_{\max} - x_{\min}}, \quad (1)$$

where x_i – the initial value of the feature of the i -th object,

x'_i – normalized value of the feature i -th object,

x_{\min} – minimum feature value in the data set,

x_{\max} – maximum feature value in the data set.

The Euclidean distance was used as a of objects proximity measure x_i and x_j :

$$d_E(x_i, x_j) = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^m (x_{ik} - x_{jk})^2}, \quad (2)$$

where x_{it} and x_{jt} – k -th feature of the i -th and j -th objects,

m – number of features in the data set.

Before starting clustering according to the selected algorithm, the propensity of the data to combine into clusters is evaluated (clustering tendency).

The clustering tendency was assess using the Hopkins statistics:

$$H = \frac{\sum_n w_i}{\sum_n q_i + \sum_n w_i}, \quad (3)$$

where w_i – distance between the objects in the data set,

q_i – distance between the objects in the dataset and the generated objects;

n – number of objects in the data set.

The work of clustering algorithms is iterative. In the agglomerative hierarchical algorithm, clusters that are closest to each other are merged at each stage. When combining them, the Complete method was used, and the optimal number of clusters is determined as the difference between the number of objects in the data set and the number of the iteration stage at which the first sharp jump in the distance of the combined clusters [7].

During the implementation of the k-means algorithm, the optimal number of clusters is determined by the Elbow method, and the optimality of the division into clusters is determined by optimizing the objective function [8]:

$$J = \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{i=1}^{n_j} d^2(x_{ij}, c_j), \quad (4)$$

where $d(x_{ij}, c_j)$ – distance between the i -th object of the j -th cluster and its centroid,

k – number of clusters, n_j – number of objects in the j -th cluster.

The result of the analysis of the vulnerability of population groups for the purpose of determining priorities in the distribution of humanitarian aid using the developed web application is demonstrated for a data set containing information on 300 people from the frontline zone (Fig. 1). The calculated value of the Hopkins test was found to be 0.3, indicating that the data have a good tendency to cluster.

	surname	danger	childs	health	income	tax	age	satis
0	Poliak	99.0	0.0	14.51	12326.0	10.00	56.0	3.8
1	Dmytrenko	58.0	2.0	2.50	16578.0	10.00	38.0	5.0
2	Kucher	17.0	0.0	1.45	21685.0	4.44	53.0	3.8
3	Korniychenko	81.0	1.0	6.82	13520.0	10.00	47.0	3.4
4	Kuzmenchuk	61.0	0.0	2.04	22096.0	4.22	75.0	3.0

Figure 1. Input data set

For the k-means algorithm, the application of the elbow method showed that the optimal number of clusters is three (Fig. 2), and the distribution of persons by clusters was as follows: 121, 102, 77.

Figure 2. Using the elbow method to determine the optimal number of clusters

In the case of choosing a hierarchical clustering algorithm for the analysis of this data set, a dendrogram is displayed that reflects the iteration stages of this algorithm (Fig. 3). According to the results of the conducted hierarchical cluster analysis, the optimal number of clusters, equal to three, was also obtained. The

system provides for the output and viewing of the contents of each cluster for the interpretation of the obtained results (Fig. 4). The analysis of the content of the clusters obtained by the two algorithms showed that the distribution of persons by clusters in them coincides by 84%. Which indicates a qualitative cluster analysis.

Figure 3. Histogram of the conducted hierarchical cluster analysis

	danger	childs	health	income	tax	age	satis	KMean_clusterid
0	0.99	0.0	1.450	12326.0	10.00	56.0	0.38	0
1	0.58	2.0	0.250	16578.0	10.00	38.0	0.50	1
2	0.17	0.0	0.145	21685.0	4.44	53.0	0.38	2
3	0.81	1.0	0.682	13520.0	10.00	47.0	0.34	0
4	0.61	0.0	0.204	22096.0	4.22	75.0	0.30	0

Figure 4. Output of identifiers of belonging to clusters for objects from the input data set

The derivation of the average values of the characteristics of the clusters makes it possible to interpret the results in order to determine the cluster whose persons need priority help (Fig. 5, Fig. 6). In the case of a

limited number of assistance packages, distribution is carried out for the cluster that contains the most vulnerable categories of persons in the order determined by their proximity to the centroid of the cluster.

	danger	childs	health	income	tax	age	satis
KMean_clusterid							
0	0.753820	0.052342	0.509981	0.167761	0.303343	0.593011	0.247934
1	0.627013	0.822511	0.400474	0.297555	0.267108	0.283436	0.357492
2	0.208824	0.098039	0.097006	0.620718	0.133332	0.601995	0.618088

Figure 5. Derivation of average values of clusters features

Figure 6. Visualization of the average values of clusters features

The analysis carried out allows us to state that the greatest need for humanitarian aid is found in the first cluster - there is the lowest level of life satisfaction, the highest indicators of expenses and worse health indicators. Figure 7 shows the list of persons selected for humanitarian aid according to the k-means algorithm.

surname	danger	childs	health	income	tax	age	satis
34 Iryna Kovalenko	80.0	0.0	7.4	12349.0	10.0	49.0	3.1
85 Oksana Kovalchuk	95.0	0.0	6.28	12204.0	10.0	52.0	3.8
298 Viktor Kovalenko	81.0	0.0	10.98	10079.0	10.0	53.0	2.8
65 Tatiana Shevchenko	76.0	0.0	4.61	14124.0	10.0	60.0	3.0
275 Julia Bondarenko	63.0	0.0	6.6	13946.0	10.0	61.0	2.6
247 Dmytro Melnyk	88.0	0.0	5.44	13981.0	10.0	45.0	4.1
154 Viktor Kovalenko	92.0	0.0	10.33	10844.0	10.0	53.0	2.6
116 Olga Lysenko	77.0	0.0	6.57	18190.0	10.0	48.0	4.7
4 Olena Bondarenko	81.0	1.0	6.82	13520.0	10.0	47.0	3.4
227 Julia Bondarenko	56.0	0.0	5.25	14223.0	10.0	56.0	2.8
11 Vitaly Petrenko	79.0	0.0	5.78	12021.0	10.0	67.0	3.8
217 Ihor Shevchenko	89.0	0.0	9.6	11326.0	10.0	57.0	1.7
139 Dmytro Bondarenko	97.0	0.0	9.47	13982.0	10.0	62.0	2.7
61 Vitaly Kovalchuk	86.0	0.0	10.02	11880.0	10.0	41.0	2.1
244 Oksana Lysenko	97.0	0.0	9.91	14412.0	10.0	52.0	2.0
164 Olga Lysenko	72.0	0.0	3.96	15033.0	10.0	42.0	3.9
143 Volodymyr Melnyk	61.0	0.0	4.93	18943.0	10.0	53.0	4.1
214 Oksana Petrenko	83.0	1.0	10.4	14734.0	10.0	50.0	3.3
223 Andriy Melnyk	94.0	0.0	5.44	12235.0	10.0	62.0	4.3
187 Dmytro Bondarenko	96.0	0.0	8.0	8859.0	10.0	57.0	1.7

Figure 7. List of persons to receive humanitarian aid, determined by the *k*-means algorithm

Thus, the use of clustering facilitates more accurate and rapid identification of important patterns and ensures the optimal distribution of humanitarian aid in situations where time is a critical factor. This simplifies decision-making on the distribution of humanitarian aid and saves the time of volunteers who work directly in frontline areas.

The developed humanitarian aid distribution system allows to improve the mechanism of determining humanitarian aid needs and optimize the distribution of necessary resources. The web application provides an opportunity for volunteers to download data on persons in need of assistance, perform their analysis, identify groups of people related to their needs, and form a sequence of resource distribution in accordance with the established priority of vulnerability of population groups.

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